

Association of Oral Health Status in Young Adult Asthmatic Patient of Moradabad City

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Abstract

Background: Asthma is a chronic inflammatory airway disease that may exert meaningful effects beyond the respiratory tract, particularly in the oral cavity. Long-term inhaler use, mouth breathing, reduced salivary flow, and altered oral pH have all been linked with caries, periodontal breakdown, and mucosal changes.

Aim: To assess the association between oral health status and asthma among young adults of Moradabad city, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Materials and Methods: An observational case-control study was conducted among 268 participants aged 20-40 years, comprising 134 asthmatic patients and 134 non-asthmatic controls. Oral examination was performed using WHO criteria (1997) for dentition and periodontal assessment. The study received ethical approval from the Institutional Ethics and Review Board of Kothiwal Dental College and Research Centre.

Results: The two groups were comparable in age and gender distribution. Asthmatic participants showed a significantly higher mean number of decayed teeth, more advanced periodontal pocketing, greater attachment loss, and a higher prevalence of oral mucosal lesions. Bleeding on probing did not differ significantly between groups.

Conclusion: Young adults with asthma demonstrated poorer oral health than non-asthmatic controls. The findings support integrating oral screening, preventive counseling, and dental referral into routine asthma care.

Keywords: Asthma; Oral Health; Dental Caries; Periodontal Disease; Young Adults; Case-Control Study

Introduction

Asthma is a common chronic inflammatory disorder characterized by airway hyperresponsiveness, episodic air-flow limitation, and variable symptoms such as wheeze, cough, and dyspnea. Although traditionally regarded as a respiratory condition, asthma has increasingly been recognized as a disease with wider systemic consequences, including measurable effects on oral health. The oral cavity, being constantly exposed to saliva, microbiota, and inhaled medications, is especially vulnerable to these changes.

Several mechanisms may explain the link between asthma and oral disease. Mouth breathing and airway inflammation can reduce salivary protection, while inhaled corticosteroids and bronchodilators may alter oral pH, microbial balance, and mucosal immunity. These changes can promote caries, plaque retention, gingival inflammation, periodontal pocketing, and even oral mucosal lesions. In younger adults, these risks are clinically important because oral disease during this period may affect quality of life,

function, and long-term oral health trajectories.

Figure 1: Representative clinical photograph of a carious lesion in an asthmatic participant.

Materials and Methods

This observational case control study included residents of Moradabad city aged 20-40 years. The case group comprised individuals with asthma for more than 5 years who were receiving inhalers alone or inhalers combined with medication. The control group included age eligible non-asthmatic individuals.

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duals. Participants with systemic conditions that could confound oral disease, recent dental treatment, recent antibiotic use, pregnancy, or lactation were excluded. The final sample size was 268, with 134 participants in each group.

Figure 2. Study participant recruitment and allocation process.

CLINICAL EXAMINATION PROTOCOL

Figure 3. Clinical Examination and Data Collection Protocol

Clinical assessment was performed using a mouth mirror, explorer, CPI probe, tweezers, gloves, kidney tray, and WHO 1997 pro forma. Periodontal status and dentition status were recorded according to WHO criteria. The examiner was trained and calibrated, with excellent intra-examiner agreement reported for dentition status and Community Periodontal Index recording. Ethical approval was obtained before data collection, and informed consent was secured from participants or guardians.

Outcome	Asthma group	Non-asthma group	Statistical note
Mean decayed teeth	2.64 ± 2.05	1.97 ± 1.33	Significant, p = 0.002
Bleeding on probing present	64.2%	70.9%	Not significant, p = 0.240
Grade III periodontal pockets	35.1%	0%	Significant, p < 0.001
Grade III attachment loss	28.4%	0%	Significant, p < 0.001
Oral lesions present	14.2%	0%	Significant, p < 0.001

Table 1: Core Oral health findings

Results

The two study groups were well matched for age and sex. The mean age was 29.38 ± 6.30 years in the asthma group and 30.81 ± 6.05 years in the non-asthma group, with no statistically significant difference. Gender distribution was also comparable. Most asthmatic participants had disease durations between 5 and 8 years, with 7 years being the most common duration.

Duration of Asthma (Years)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
5	32	23.9
6	27	20.1
7	46	34.3
8	29	21.6
Total	134	100.0

Table 2 : Distribution of asthma duration among young adult asthmatic participants included in the study. The majority of subjects had a disease duration of 7 years (34.3%).

The mean number of decayed teeth was significantly higher in the asthmatic group, indicating a greater caries burden. Bleeding on probing occurred in both groups at similar frequencies, and this difference was not statistically significant. However, periodontal pocket depth showed a marked divergence: Grade III pockets were seen in more than one-third of asthmatic participants and in none of the controls. Similarly, Grade III attachment loss was observed only among asthmatic individuals. Oral mucosal lesions were also restricted to the asthma group.

Figure 4: Clinical photograph showing periodontal pocketing and gingival inflammation in an asthmatic participant.

Figure 5: Clinical image of an oral mucosal lesion identified in the asthma group.

Discussion

The present study demonstrates that young adult asthmatic patients carry a significantly heavier oral disease burden than their non-asthmatic peers. The higher decayed teeth score supports the concept that asthma and its treatment may contribute to an oral environment favorable for caries development. Possible explanations include medication associated xerostomia, lower salivary buffering capacity, altered oral microflora, and reduced self-care during symptomatic periods. Similar patterns have been reported in prior studies across both adult and pediatric populations.

Periodontal findings were equally notable. Although bleeding on probing did not differ significantly, deeper pockets and greater attachment loss were substantially more common among asthmatic participants. This suggests that chronic asthma may be linked less to superficial gingival inflammation alone and more to cumulative periodontal destruction. The literature supports this pattern, with cohort and case control studies describing higher periodontal risk in asthma, particularly in individuals exposed to long-term inhaled corticosteroids and persistent airway inflammation.

A major strength of this study is the group-matched design with comparable age and sex distribution, which reduces confounding. A limitation, however, is the absence of individual level matching and the inability to fully account for differences in oral hygiene behavior, disease severity, and medication dosage. Even so, the consistency of the findings across caries, periodontal, and mucosal domains makes the observed association clinically persuasive.

Oral Health Parameter	Asthmatic Group	Non-Asthmatic Group	p-value
Mean Decayed Teeth	2.64 ± 2.05	1.97 ± 1.33	0.002*
Periodontal Pocket Depth (Grade III)	35.1%	0%	<0.001*
Attachment Loss (Grade III)	28.4%	0%	<0.001*
Oral Mucosal Lesions	14.2%	0%	<0.001*

* Statistically Significant

Table 3 : Comparison of major oral health indicators between asthmatic and non-asthmatic participants.

Conclusion

Young adult patients with asthma in Moradabad city showed poorer oral health than non-asthmatic controls, with higher caries experience, more advanced periodontal breakdown, and greater occurrence of oral mucosal lesions. The findings justify routine dental screening for asthmatic patients and reinforce the need for coordinated medical dental care. Oral hygiene instruction, post-inhaler mouth rinsing, fluoride based prevention, and periodic periodontal evaluation should become standard elements of asthma management.

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